

Figure 6. Example Data for Publication Year, Country, ToxRTool Use			
Authors	Year	Country	ToxRTool Use
Schneider et al.	2009	Germany	F
Burns and Davies	2021	USA	M
Card and Magnuson	2010	Canada	M
Fewtrell et al.	2022	United Kingdom	F
Gimenes et al.	2022	Brazil	F
Kirkland et al.	2020	United Kingdom	R
Kose et al.	2023	France	F

Figure 6. Example Data for Publication Year, Country, ToxRTool Use. For the Burns and Davies 2021 publication, its first author's country is USA and this publication Modified (M) ToxRTool. The options for 'ToxRTool Use' includes: 1) Followed (F) ToxRTool, 2) Modified (M) ToxRTool, 3) Added (A) to ToxRTool, 4) Referenced prior publication's modification (R), or 5) No changes were made (none (N)).